

Short-Term Chemical Changes in Sandy Soil Following Composted Solid Winery Waste Application and NPK Fertilisation under Swiss Chard Cultivation

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Abstract

Soil fertility challenges, particularly for smallholder farmers, are often addressed with inorganic fertilisers, which can lead to soil degradation. This study investigates a sustainable alternative by comparing the short-term effects of NPK fertilisation and two different application rates of composted solid winery waste on sandy soil cultivated with Swiss chard. The study used a randomised complete block design with four treatments (control, NPK, low-rate composted solid winery waste, and high-rate composted solid winery waste). Soil samples were taken at bi-weekly intervals over eight weeks (4 intervals) to assess chemical properties, including pH, phosphorus (P), potassium (K), and various exchangeable cations. The results showed that the NPK fertiliser provided a rapid but temporary increase in nutrients, and it also caused significant soil acidification and a decline in P availability. In contrast, the high-rate composted solid winery waste application effectively ameliorated soil pH ($p < 0.05$) and provided a more gradual and sustained release of nutrients, particularly P and K, throughout the observation period. The low-rate composted solid winery waste was found to be insufficient to produce significant chemical changes. These findings demonstrate that utilising composted solid winery waste as a soil amendment, in the short term, is a more environmentally friendly approach than relying on inorganic fertilisers. This aligns with the principles of a circular economy and turns a waste product into a valuable resource for improving soil health and fertility.

Keywords: inorganic fertiliser, solid winery waste, Swiss chard, soil chemical properties, circular economy.

Introduction

Soil fertility is a leading production challenge faced by many smallholder farmers in Africa (Vanalauwe and Giller, 2006). Soil fertility declines have been linked to inappropriate land use, such as monocropping, inadequate fertiliser use, and complete removal of crop residues (Alemineu and Alemayehu, 2020). Soil fertility declines lead to reduced crop yields, which is challenging given the need to feed the ever-growing human population in Africa (Raimi et al., 2017; Chaudhary et al., 2023). In recent years, soil fertility declines have largely been ameliorated using inorganic fertilisers (Sindesi et al., 2023). Over-reliance on inorganic fertilisers can cause soil degradation, including reduced organic matter and soil acidification, which leads to decreased fertility and plant health (Kopittke et al., 2019). In response to these challenges, the global movement towards a circular economy advocates for systems where materials are never treated as waste, and natural processes are regenerated (De Sa and Korinek, 2021). This approach encourages the sustainable and environmentally friendly use of organic by-products from various industries.

The wine industry produces various types of winery waste, including solid and liquid wastewater. This winery waste is normally discarded into the fields or burned, thus causing environmental problems (Genisheva et al., 2023). Liquid winery waste poses a direct threat to aquatic life through oxygen depletion and water pollution from its high organic content, low pH, and salinity (Ioannou et al., 2015). Solid winery waste has phytotoxicity due to high levels of organic acids and phenols. Furthermore, solid winery waste that is not properly treated could pollute the soil, air and water (Zingela, 2006). Composting solid winery waste for crop cultivation is an alternative to landfill and burning for waste disposal (Bertran et al., 2004). The application of compost increases the percentages of organic matter, nutrient levels (providing a slow fertilisation action over a long period of time), microbial biomass and improves the soils' physical properties (aeration, water holding capacity, etc.) (Bertran et al., 2004). While the use of compost is known to improve soil health, there is limited research directly comparing the specific chemical changes in a single soil type of soils fertilised with NPK fertiliser versus different composted solid winery waste, especially under the cultivation of a specific crop such as Swiss chard. This study evaluates and compares the short-term effects of NPK fertilisation and two different rates of composted solid winery waste on the chemical properties of sandy soil under Swiss chard cultivation.

Materials and Methods

Experimental site:

A field experiment was conducted at the Agricultural Research Council (ARC), Bien Donn Farm, Paarl, Western Cape, South Africa (33.84274°S and 18.98425° E). The study investigated the effects of composted solid winery waste and inorganic fertiliser (NPK) on the chemical characteristics of sandy soil cultivated with Swiss chard. Swiss chard was cultivated for 8 weeks (April to June). Paarl is characterised by a Mediterranean climate, with cool, rainy (approximately 450-500mm annually) winters and hot, dry summers (Harebottle et al., 2008). Most of the rain falls between May and October. Winter temperatures can drop to a

minimum of 10°C, while summer temperatures can go up to 35°C. The climate in this region is ideal for agricultural production and supports the region's wine and fruit production.

Composted Solid Winery Waste Production

The composted solid winery waste was produced using the method described in the study by Masowa et al. (2016). By co-composting filter materials (FMs), consisting of perlite and diatomaceous earth obtained from winery waste, with grape marc and chopped grapevine pruning canes used as bulking material (BM). FMs were mixed with the BMs at 40% FM and 60% BM. The composting was done in a static heap, with a heap measuring 2 x 1.5 x 1 m (L x W x H) over 13 weeks under aerobic-thermophilic conditions without turning. Additionally, temperature was maintained at 38.3 °C during the composting period, and compost was maintained at 50 to 60% moisture content.

Experimental design:

The study was arranged in a randomised complete block design (RCBD) with four treatments replicated four times. Each replicate was assigned to a 4 m * 4 m sub-plot, and the total experimental field was 256 m². The control treatment had no compost and no inorganic fertiliser application. T1 was applied with inorganic 2:3:4 (30) - 5g Zn% fertilisers (500 kg ha⁻¹) before planting and 175 kg ha⁻¹ LAN (28) at 4 and 8 weeks after planting. T2 was applied with 2.18 t ha⁻¹ of composted solid winery waste, while T3 was applied with 8.72 t ha⁻¹ of composted solid winery waste. The chemical composition of the used winery waste is shown in the Table. 1 below. The chemical composition of the composted solid winery waste used in this study presented two primary concerns: high alkalinity (pH 10.3) and a high sodium (Na) concentration (10525.50 mg kg⁻¹).

Table 1. Chemical composition of the composted solid winery waste

Characteristic	Unit	Value
Total Organic Carbon (C)	%	11.9
Total Nitrogen (N)	%	1.23
C/N Ratio	–	10
Na	mg kg ⁻¹	10525.5
Ca	%	0.75
Mg	%	0.15
K	%	6.57
P	%	0.48
pH (KCl)	–	10.3

Agronomic practices:

Before planting, the field was tilled using a disc plough, followed by a disk harrow 4 weeks before seedling transplanting to achieve fine tilth. Composted solid winery waste was also applied 1 week before seedling transplanting. Healthy vigorous six-week-old Swiss chard seedlings were transplanted at a spacing of 50 cm between plants and 70 cm between rows. Tension-meters were installed at soil depth 0-30 cm in each block to monitor soil moisture for irrigation scheduling. Irrigation was applied using micro-jets (1.5 L hr⁻¹), and irrigation was done three times a week. Weeds were controlled using a hand spade when needed, insect pests were controlled using a registered insecticide, alpha-cypermethrin (pyrethroid) 100 g L⁻¹

(ALPHA-THRIN 100 SC ©) mixed with 3 ml ALPHA, 10 ml liquid detergent and 25 L of water.

Data Collection:

Soil chemical composition: A composite soil sample was taken using a soil auger at soil depth 0-30 cm before seedling transplanting. Representative samples, three from each subplot, were taken 2, 4, 6 and 8 weeks after transplanting. The soil was analysed for phosphorus (P), potassium (K), sodium (Na), calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), and soil pH. Soil nitrogen (N) was not analysed after the application of treatments. The analysis methods used were the ICP-OES method for K, and the Bray II method for P. Soil exchangeable Ca, Mg, and Na were extracted using 1.0 N ammonium (NH₄⁺) acetate. While soil pH was measured using the 1.0 N KCl method (Non-affiliated Soil Analysis Work Committee, 1990). The baseline soil chemical characteristics for the soil are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Baseline soil properties

Parameter	Unit	Value
Soil Depth (cm)	cm	0–30
pH (KCl)		6.00
P (Bray II)	(mg kg ⁻¹)	25.30
K	(mg kg ⁻¹)	54.00
Na	(cmol (+) kg ⁻¹)	0.06
Ca	(cmol (+) kg ⁻¹)	3.92
Mg	(cmol (+) kg ⁻¹)	0.88

Data analysis

Data were subjected to an analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SAS (version 9.4, SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC, USA, 2000). Treatment means were separated using Fisher's least significant difference (post-hoc test), and the difference was calculated at the 5% level. A probability level of 5% was considered significant for all tests of significance.

Results and Discussion

Soil pH response to composted solid winery waste and NPK fertilisation

Soil pH is the most important factor for crop growth in agriculture, as it influences the availability of nutrients to plants (Dewangan et al., 2023). Soil pH is influenced by a variety of factors, such as inherent factors, which include parent material, climate and soil texture. These inherent factors provide the soil with its initial chemical characteristics. Other factors which influence soil pH in agriculture are organic matter inputs, production practices such as the use of N-based fertilisers, cropping systems, and tillage practices (Oshunsanya, 2018). The application of nitrogenous fertilisers has been observed to increase soil acidity (Sharma et al., 2022). Organic compost applications have been linked to reduced soil acidity (Hassin et al., 2022). Organic composts also act as a pH buffer, helping to stabilise soil pH rather than causing drastic changes (Dvořáčková et al., 2022). The sandy soil used for this study was slightly acidic, with a pH of 6; however, it was still within the optimal range for Swiss chard growth. In week 2, all the treatment soils showed reductions in soil pH, with the control, T2

and T3 showing less reduction than T1. This may be attributed to tillage or irrigation practices used on the soil to prepare it for transplanting.

The pH of soils which were applied with NPK fertiliser and later with LAN (T1) reduced ($p < 0.05$), becoming more acidic, from the initial soil pH (Fig. 1). The acidification of the soils by the second week can be linked to the N component in the NPK fertiliser used. NPK fertilisers contain N in the form of NH_4^+ or compounds that convert to NH_4^+ in the soil, such as urea. The process that causes the decrease in pH is called nitrification, as the process produces protons (H^+), which increase the acidity (Grzyb et al., 2021; Mshweshwe et al., 2025; Sindesi et al., 2025a). Treatments 2 and 3 only showed significant pH changes in week 4, where T3 showed superior soil pH amelioration than the rest of the treatments. The application of composted solid winery waste increased soil pH by adding alkaline materials, such as K (Ho et al., 2022). The composted solid winery waste used had high K (6.57%) content along with an alkaline nature (pH 10.3). These results support earlier findings (Bustamente et al., 2008; Novoa-Munoz et al., 2008), in which acidic soil was rectified over time utilising compost from winery waste sources on a few crop species. This effect is not clearly seen on T2 and can be attributed to the amount of compost applied. T3 had about four (4) times the amount of compost applied on T2. It is possible that the amount of compost applied to T2 was insufficient for a drastic pH change.

Figure 1. Soil pH (KCl) responses to composted solid winery waste and NPK fertilisation. Bars with the same letter show no significance at $p < 0.05$

Effect of composted solid winery waste and NPK fertilisation on soil P

P is a crop-limiting nutrient; it is inefficiently used by plants due to soil immobilisation and fixation, which result in low bioavailability (Mardamootoo et al., 2021). In plants, P stimulates root development, as a result, it facilitates improved moisture and nutrient uptake (Mashece et al., 2025). Soil P availability is influenced by several factors such as soil pH, temperature, salinity, and organic matter content (Xie et al., 2022). Among these, the application of NPK fertilisers, apart from directly increasing soil P, also influences soil pH, while the application of composted solid winery waste influences both soil pH and organic matter content. Figure 2 illustrates the results of the influence of composted solid winery waste and NPK fertiliser on soil P. In week 2, the NPK treatment showed higher ($p < 0.05$) levels of soil P than the other treatments. This is because NPK provides plant-available P, spiking the availability of soil P for a short time. When P-based fertilisers are applied, a portion of the P is in its soluble form ($\text{Ca}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2$). This allows for an immediate

increase in the concentration of plant-available P in soils (Schipanski, 2021). The spike in availability is a direct result of the chemical composition of the used fertiliser, making the nutrient readily accessible for plant uptake. By the fourth week, T2 observed a drastic decrease ($p < 0.05$) in plant-available P, which was maintained until the eighth week. The decrease may be due to P fixation and immobilisation within the soil (Li et al., 2023; Chatterjee et al., 2014). In fixation, P ions react with other minerals in the soil, such as Ca in alkaline soils, or iron (Fe) and aluminium (Al) in acidic soils (Li et al., 2023). In immobilisation, soluble P is taken up by soil microbes to support their own growth, therefore, incorporating P into their biomass, making it temporarily unavailable to plants (Chatterjee et al., 2014). The former is considered the main cause of the T2 observed P trend, as the soil pH during this time was acidic. This is further confirmed by the optimal soil pH range for P bioavailability, being very slightly acidic (6.5) to moderate alkalinity, 8.0 (Potash Development Association, 2005)

Figure 2. Effect of composted solid winery waste and NPK fertiliser on soil phosphorus (mg kg^{-1}). Bars with the same letter show no significance at $p < 0.05$

T3 showed a gradual increase ($p < 0.05$) in soil P from the second week to the sixth week, with a slight decrease in week 8 ($p > 0.05$). Also, T2, apart from showing less P in week 2 and week 4 than the control, it slightly increased ($p > 0.05$) plant-available P throughout the weeks. The trends indicate a slow release of P by composted solid winery waste; hence, the composted solid winery waste had 0.48% P content. Additionally, the slight decrease in plant-available P in week 8 is likely due to a combination of plant uptake, microbial activity, and P fixation as the compost breaks down. As the plant grows, P requirements increase to support the energy-intensive processes of cell division and structural development in newly formed tissues (Malhotra et al., 2018). P fixation and immobilisation may also explain the decrease, as the newly released inorganic P is still subject to the same soil fixation processes as synthetic fertilisers. As micro-organisms reach peak activity and continue to proliferate, they assimilate available soil P to support their growth (Montreemuk et al., 2024)

Effect of composted solid winery waste soil application and NPK fertilisation on soil K

K plays an important role in plant growth and metabolism, including enzyme activation, protein synthesis, stomatal regulation and ion absorption (Prajapati and Modi,

2012). K availability in soil is influenced by numerous factors, including soil chemistry, physical properties, biological factors, and management practices (Mouhamad, 2016). In this study, soil K increased with time for all the treatments; only T2 and T3 showed a significant increase (Table 2). This may be due to accelerated mineral weathering, which is influenced by tillage (Liu et al., 2021). Additionally, the slightly higher ($p>0.05$) amounts of K in the NPK amended treatments than the control can be attributed to the available K within the NPK fertiliser. Furthermore, the increased application of composted solid winery waste containing 6.57 % K also increased soil K. Hence, the values of soil K 8 weeks after transplanting the seedlings are almost four times greater on T3 than on T2. This is partially because T2 received four times less composted solid winery waste than T3. This increase ($p<0.05$) in K in the compost treatments could also potentially be attributed to increased microbial activity brought on by the addition of organic wastes, which could hasten K cycling. Additionally, these findings are consistent with the findings of Bustamente et al. (2008), which indicated that high soil K concentrations could be linked to a high proportion of winery and distillery waste products with high K concentrations.

Table 3. Influence of composted solid winery waste and NPK fertiliser on soil K (mg kg^{-1}).

Week	2	4	6	8
Control	51.25 ^g	53.50 ^g	53.75 ^g	56.25 ^{fg}
T1	79.75 ^{efg}	68.00 ^{fg}	61.50 ^{fg}	63.00 ^{fg}
T2	64.00 ^{fg}	87.50 ^{ef}	140.25 ^d	142.00 ^d
T3	111.75 ^{de}	321.50 ^c	362.0 ^b	414.75 ^a

Note: Means in the same column with different superscripts are significantly different from each other ($P<0.05$)

Soil exchangeable cations response to composted solid winery waste and NPK fertilisation

The exchangeability of cations in the soil is governed by the cation exchange capacity (CEC) as well as soil pH (Sindesi et al., 2022). Exchangeable Ca was reduced from the initial soil exchangeable Ca of 3.92 cmol (+) kg^{-1} for all treatments. The consistent decrease across all treatments is primarily attributed to the high Ca demand observed in Swiss chard during its active growth phase (Pokluda and Kuben, 2002; Mzoughi et al., 2019). There were no significant ($p>0.05$) changes in exchangeable Ca across treatments (Fig. 3) nor with passing time, although T2 showed slightly better ($p>0.05$) exchangeable Ca from week 4 onwards. This is because the used NPK fertiliser did not contain any Ca. Additionally, the lack of response to the composted treatments is directly linked to the compost composition. The composted solid winery waste had almost negligible Ca of 0.75%. This value is significantly lower than the 1.5-3.5% range required for high-quality compost directed towards improving soil mineral status (Sultanaa et al., 2022). Consequently, the compost application failed to supply sufficient Ca to counteract the continuous Swiss chard uptake. It could not meet the Swiss chard Ca demand and replenish the soil's exchangeable pool. Therefore, treatment and time did not influence the availability of Ca.

Figure 3. Responses of Ca (cmol (+) kg⁻¹) to composted solid winery waste and NPK fertilisation. Bars with the same letter show no significance at $p < 0.05$

Regardless, T3, with the highest composted solid winery waste, had the highest ($p < 0.05$) exchangeable Na (Fig. 4) among the treatments throughout the observation weeks. The used composted solid winery waste had high levels of Na (10525.50 mg kg⁻¹). Furthermore, exchangeable Na remained constant on this treatment, while for the other treatments, there were slight fluctuations, particularly in the control. The fluctuations may be caused by a variety of factors, such as leaching, plant uptake and salt accumulation after moisture evaporation (Tarolli et al., 2024). Soil exchangeable Mg also decreased from the initial soil Mg (Fig. 5). This observed decrease is linked to plant uptake, while the lack of significant treatment effect is associated with the limited Mg in the applied compost. The composted solid winery waste contained only 0.15% Mg. This level was less than the standard range required for compost intended for field application, a range of 0.25 to 0.7% as noted in the work by Sullivan et al. (2018). As a result, even the high compost application (T3) rate failed to provide enough Mg to mitigate the nutrients removed by Swiss chard. Overall, exchangeable Mg did not show any significant differences across treatment and across time. However, a slightly higher ($p > 0.05$) Mg value was observed on the control treatment in week 6. The non-significant findings suggest that over the short term, the inherent characteristics of the sandy soil were the main drivers of exchangeable Mg behaviour. Specifically, the low CEC and natural buffering mechanisms offset the effect of the low-nutrient-content amendments. Nevertheless, these results contradict earlier findings by Dikinya et al. (2010), who found increased Mg with increasing rates of composted chicken manure.

Figure 4. Effect of winery waste and NPK fertilisation on soil exchangeable Na (cmol (+) kg⁻¹). Bars with the same letter show no significance at $p < 0.05$

Figure 5. Responses of soil exchangeable Mg (cmol (+) kg⁻¹) to composted solid winery waste application and NPK fertilisation. Bars with the same letter show no significance at $p < 0.05$

Implications and limitations regarding N dynamics

A key aspect of this study was to compare the effect of NPK fertilisation with composted solid winery waste. As such, N dynamics are a major driver of the observed soil chemistry and Swiss chard response. However, a critical limitation of the current study is the omission of soil N, which is essential for evaluating the availability of N over time. Nevertheless, the role of N on pH has been inferred based on the pH results. The process of nitrification, which converts the NH₄-based N sources into nitrate, releases hydrogen ions (H⁺) or protons, thereby increasing soil acidity and reducing soil pH (Mshweshwe et al., 2025; Sindesi et al., 2025a). While the high-rate compost treatment (T3), despite having a low C: N ratio of 10, had a highly alkaline pH of 10.3. This high alkalinity may have exceeded any potential acidifying effects from N mineralisation, resulting in pH amelioration. N is the primary component of protein and nucleic acids in plants (Sindesi et al., 2025b). It plays a crucial role in regulating meristematic cell activity and promoting cell division (Sindesi et al., 2025a). The contrasting N supply, rapidly available inorganic N from the NPK treatment versus slow-release organic N from the compost, was expected to create differing growth patterns. This expectation is consistent with the findings reported by Mungoche et al. (2023). The dynamic growth expected from the NPK treatment was observed only on one Swiss chard growth parameter, the number of leaves per plant, at week 2 (Ndololwana et al., 2026). This observation is linked to the availability of N applied before the transplanting of seedlings. Nevertheless, after week 2, this observation disappeared, suggesting a potential leaching of N or reduced N efficiency linked to reduced soil moisture. This is consistent with the suggestion by Wang et al. (2025) that when soil moisture is in a restricted state, excessive application of N fertiliser not only fails to promote plant growth but also produces antagonistic effects. Soil moisture may easily evaporate in soils with reduced or minimal levels of organic matter (Zhang et al., 2021).

Conclusion

This study assessed the short-term effects of inorganic NPK fertiliser and two application rates of composted solid winery waste on the chemical properties of a sandy soil under Swiss chard production. The findings provide valuable initial insight into the immediate

chemical responses of sandy soil to composted winery waste; however, several limitations are acknowledged. Firstly, the experimental duration of 8 weeks captures only short-term changes and does not reflect long-term soil responses or the eventual fate of the high Na introduced by the compost. Secondly, the trial was conducted on a single sandy soil type; therefore, results cannot be generalised to soils with different textures or chemical characteristics. Lastly, this study focused on soil chemistry only; the absence of soil N and C data following compost application, as well as the lack of crop yield measurements, limits the ability to link observed chemical improvements to agronomic performance. Additionally, worth noting, the chemical composition of the composted solid winery waste presented two key concerns: high alkalinity (pH 10.3) and critically elevated Na content ($10525.50 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$). While the high pH, driven by basic cations such as K, effectively corrected the initial soil acidity, the immediate benefit is offset by the increased exchangeable Na, which poses a severe potential long-term salinity and sodicity hazard. This increased exchangeable Na warrants further investigation to determine whether these benefits persist and, most importantly, to evaluate the eventual fate and potential toxicity risks associated with the high Na loading over multiple cropping seasons. Despite these constraints, clear trends emerged. NPK fertiliser delivered an immediate but short-lived nutrient boost and contributed to soil acidification and reduced P availability over time, likely due to fixation and microbial immobilisation. In contrast, the high-rate compost treatment produced the most comprehensive improvements, including pH amelioration and a sustained release of nutrients, especially P and K, throughout the study period. The lower compost rate produced minimal chemical change across most soil parameters. This observation suggests that the minimum threshold application rate of compost necessary to produce a significant soil chemistry change was not met. This further emphasises the importance of adequate application levels for organic amendments in nutrient-poor sandy soils. Overall, the results demonstrate that composted solid winery waste, particularly at higher application rates, offers a more sustainable soil-amendment option than inorganic NPK fertiliser. Its use contributes to the circular economy by transforming an agricultural waste product into a valuable soil-conditioning resource. Long-term studies are needed to determine whether these benefits persist over multiple cropping seasons, as well as to evaluate effects across a broader range of soil types and crops. Finally, future work should aim to identify an optimal, cost-effective application rate suitable for smallholder farmers, given that the low rate tested here was insufficient to drive meaningful soil chemical improvement. In line with this, future studies must include the change in key agronomic parameters, such as crop biomass and plant physiological observations. These performance indicators are necessary for a holistic assessment of the agronomic implications of the observed soil chemical improvements.

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